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of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

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Not Just a Pretty Face

Tourism is more than beauty seen,
It calls for brains, a mind serene.
Confidence in strangers met,
From walks of life we'll not forget.

Patience steady, calm, and true,
Initiative in all you do.
Guts to face a world so wide,
Where dreams and reality collide.

Jobs you prayed for may not appear,
Yet other paths may draw you near.
Long hours, low pay, schedules tight,
Still you must shine, still do it right.

Appearance, charm, the constant care,
Acostly burden many bear.
Some will stay, some walk away,
But those who love it choose to stay.

For passion fuels the heart and mind,
Resilience grows with every grind.
Tourism is a test, a daring art,
For those with courage, strength, and heart.